

Working Group Connection with policies and strategies

DIHNET.EU aims at developing a set of tools and boosting the collaboration of the different Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), DIH networks and other key DIH stakeholders in Europe. The DIHNET Working Groups (WG) will identify and target challenges that require the input from the DIH community and the different stakeholders in four main topics: “Finance and Funding opportunities”, “Collaboration activities and mechanisms”, “Connection with policies and strategies” and “Business Models and Sustainability”.

Objectives

The Working Group on “Connection with policies and strategies” focuses on exploring the challenges and actions needed to ensure alignment and coherence of DIHs to the regional, national and EU policies and strategies to digitalise industry, especially to Smart Specialisation.

What are the challenges?

- Strategies at regional, national and EU level supporting DIH collaboration.
- Mechanisms in place to support cross-border/interregional/national cooperation and technology transfer.
- Contribution of DIHs in shaping regional/national/EU digital transformation strategies.
- Involvement of DIHs for the implementation of these strategies.
- Identification of Best Practices.
- Ensuring DIH connection and alignment to the strategies.

Being part of a regional, national or European policy initiative to digitise the industry is one of the criteria for a DIH to be part of the Catalogue. How the DIH community is going to address these challenges will be discussed in the working group.

How to get engaged with the WG

You can join the DIHNET.EU Community platform at www.dihnet.eu or contact the WG coordinator.

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Join the
DIHNET.EU
online
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